

A Unique Sense of Protest in the Novels of Githa Hariharan

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Githa Hariharan's novels are full of different thematic perceptions. Her literary works have the 'wonderful sense of interest for identity' in general. She is also concerned with the degrading condition of man-woman relationship, religious orthodoxy which leads communal riots, the condition of the dalits in the society etc. There seems to be a unique blending of myth, culture, religion and history in her novels. In all her works, her voice of protest is quite evident for various reasons altogether. She seems to be more vocal and vibrant against the pathetic and compassionate condition of women in so-called male-dominated society.

Githa Hariharan's novels deal with the humanitarian attitude of the writer towards dalits, minorities and woman. She shows her inclination towards the protest against the odd and oddities existing in the society. For providing authentic perception to the novel, Githa Hariharan chooses the contemporary perceptions related to above mentioned themes in her novels.

Her novel *Fugitive Histories* deals with the condition of the minorities living different parts of the country. The novel deals with communal violence which took place after the Godhra train accident. Like so many literary activists, Githa Hariharan blames the contemporary government responsible for that communal violence for different reasons altogether. In this novel, she takes the help of documentation of the communal violence occurred after the Godhra Train accident in which more than hundreds of *Karsevakas* were burnt alive. After that Godhra accident, communal riots took place in the state and other parts of the country. In those communal riots and violence, more than four thousand innocent people were slaughtered. This novel documentizes the communal violence and riots in terms of realistic presentation. The presentation of the condition of the minorities especially women and children was really full of compassion and pathos. The anger and aggression can be visualized in the words of the Muslim women and children. There seems to be an absolute sense of anger and aggression in the mode of her presentation of the feelings and emotions of those people also.

The narrative of the novel is preoccupied with the relationship between the Hindus and the Muslims in the backdrop of the division of the country. The loss of faith between these two communities is quite evident in the narration of the novel for different reasons altogether. The horror and terror that existed in the minds of the people belonging to both

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communities is quite obvious in the narrative of the novel. Reshma, Zainub Bano, Najma Rajia, Nusreen Zahida Khala, Zakia, Zulekha, etc. are the real victims of time and space. The blot of riots cannot be mitigated overnight as it is evident in the presentation of Githa Hariharan. The horrible as well as compassionate experience of these women is not the fascination but the realistic presentation of the riots that took place at that time. The fear and chaos evident in the narration is quite spontaneous in nature because it tells the reality of human existence for different reasons altogether.

This novel by Githa Hariharan puts so many questions before the readers which still need suitable and appropriate answers. More than fifteen hundred years of togetherness has not provided any kind of solution to the problems related to both communities. The different backgrounds and different opinions of two different communities are certainly a matter of consideration. The beautiful combination of myth and reality decodes human living in the novel for different reasons altogether. It seems that differences between the two communities seem to be the result of the loss of faith in each-other. This gulf is widening day by day. People do not trust their respective emotions and feelings. Certainly, it is a matter of great concern because it evokes the sense of lack of understanding and mutual respect. In the recent time, it has been observed that even on the small issues, fight begins between two communities. The narrative has been created in the country about the relationship between the Hindus and the Muslims. People now say that 'India is not the fit country for living.' They say so because of the creation of the false narrative in the nation. The so-called concept of secularism has been mocked by the nationalist people.

Githa Hariharan is quite different from her contemporaries because of so many reasons altogether. Her contemporaries like — Manju Kapur, Chitra Banerjee and Jumpa Lahiri — show their much concern towards the depiction of social and psychological issues in their novels. For instance, almost all the novels of Manju Kapur — *Home*, *Difficult Daughters*, *A Married Woman*, *Custody*, *The Immigrants* and *Brothers* — seem to be the social documentation of the contemporary life with the perspectives of the writer. She analyses the problems of the women in the context of fast-changing Indian society in which there is a new look in social, cultural and moral values. The traditional and conventional values are on the verge of collapse because of the so-called modern outlook of the people. The journey of her female characters in the novel is full of struggle and dilemma and conflict which is absolutely remarkable for many reasons altogether. She shows her inclination towards the double faces of the people who are still in the stigma of orthodox mind-set and do not ready to give desired liberty to the women for different reasons altogether. A critic like M. Jaikumar rightly remarks about the thematic perceptions of Manju Kapur in these words:

“Manju Kapur’s novels are the real epitome of Indian social life which is marked by the sense of change and transformation for different reasons. Especially, her woman characters show courage to go beyond the limits of the mundane world. The kind of evolution which is visible in her novels is quite unique in telling

the tale of conflict and dilemma for which she is well-known. Her delineation of events and circumstances in her novels are full of realism also.” (*The Novels of Manju Kapur* (p. 116)

On the other hand another contemporary of Githa Hariharan is Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni who is much interested in decoding social life of the contemporary age with reference to the myth and legends. Especially her two novels — *The Palace of Illusions* and *The Forest of Enchantments* — deal with age-old Indian myth of womanhood in modern context. She would like to narrate the story of Indian womanhood in entirely new way by decoding human emotions and passion. The presentation of Drupadi in reference to *The Mahabharata* and Sita in reference to *The Ramayana* is the symbol of decoding the condition of women in new way. She would like to tell the story of womanhood in new social and cultural perspectives. There is a unique sense of newness in her depiction of human motives and motions. A critic like Amrit Deshpandey rightly remarks about the importance of the novels of Chitra Banerjee in these words:

“Chitra Banerjee’s *The Palace of Illusions* is certainly a new approach in the direction of unfolding some of the ingredients of human behaviour and predicaments in the vast domain of time and space. Chitra Banerjee’s approach towards *The Mahabharata* is quite realistic and it cannot be called her imaginative approach at all. She would like to portray all the characters involved in this epic in realistic manner and take them as human and not as divine at all. Similar is the condition with *The Palace of Illusion* which deals with the incidents and event concerned with *The Mahabharata*. (*A Critical Study of the Novels of Chitra Banerjee*, p. 129)

Manju Kapur is another contemporary of Githa Hariharan who is much interested in the presentation of the thematic perceptions related to diaspora. In her two books, she would like to show the cultural and social alienation and loneliness visible in different social and cultural setup. The mental trauma and agony one faces during her or his living abroad because of so many reasons. She would like to highlight the problem of the modern generations as evident in living abroad.

In Indian writing in English two women writer— Arundhati Roy and Githa Hariharan show this much interest and inclination towards the condition of dalits, minorities and women in the wake of modernity in Indian life. Both Arundhati Roy and Githa Hariharan are the activists who do not hesitate to write against the exploitation and humiliation faced by the dalits and minorities in the different parts of the country. Arundhati Roy’s pen is sharper in that direction to highlight such issues which are related to the people who are involved in that sort of life. Arundhati Roy raises her voice against the exploitation of the dalits and minorities her the police and the government officials also.

There is a unique flavour of protest and activism in the writings of Githa Hariharan because of her way of presentation of the contemporary detail in relation to the mythical references. The use of myth enables her to decode such life in the modern scenario. The exploitation of woman, minorities and dalits is not new in India but in the modern age, the problem is more materialistic and less moralistic. The economic depravity is certainly the subject matter of great concern for different reasons altogether. In the novels of Githa Hariharan, there seems to be perfect documentation of such exploitations and humiliation faced by women, dalits and minorities due to unsympathetic and uncompassionate consideration of the people even the so-called modern civilization, she is of the view that even after the seventy years of Independence, the condition of such people has not improved because of so many reasons altogether. She also blames the government which efforts are not conducive in this direction. The policies of the government are not as beneficial as it should be and the result is quite obvious. There must be combined efforts of the government as well as the common people. The problem presented by Mulk Raj Anand in his novel *Untouchable* is visible in Githa Hariharan's *I Have Become the Tide*.

There seems to be unique connectivity between her sense of decoding contemporary Indian life and her more active participation in that. For instance, the suicide of Rohit Bemula seems to be the source of inspiration for Githa Hariharan for different reasons altogether. Certainly, it helps her a lot to build the plot of this novel, and her co-relation with the past and mythical relation with the saint Kannadeva seems to be the superb example of delineation of her purpose attached with this novel. The life of Kannadeva is equated with the life of Satya who suicide due to the exploitation and humiliation he faced during his career as the student in the university. But his suicide has the clear motive and the novelist would like to present all these things in the manner of showing her aggression and voice of protest against the age-old blot of the caste-system in the country. Dr. Senthil, Ravi and Asha believe that one or the other day Tsunami must come and will do justice to that deprived section and shows the world the real power of humanity in the world of darkness and deprivation. The people gathered in the rally are hopeful and not hopeless at all. It is the people's voice, the voice of the mass. The novelist writes at this point in these words:

“The people voice, Senthil called it. Senthil's voice, Ravi's voice; Ravi's drum that beats like a powerful heart. The voice Asha hears coming out of the mouth. Together, they may make up a song with many verses, with or without rhyme. And the reborn: it must boom its way into the air, into Ravi's airless home and Satya's mother's lost field and Asha's father's government office. It must roll like a tsunami, finds its way into the classroom and court and parliament and Satya's grave. The rebrain is one part of the song that must be sung together. (*I Have Become the Tide*, p. 319)

In the 'Acknowledgement' of the novel, Githa Hariharan clears has steam in more vibrant manner. She is of the view that such problems still persist in the society because of the unsympathetic and uncompassionate attitude of the people. Everyone is aware with the suicide of Rohis Bemula's a student in the university of Hyderabad. According to reports shown in the print and electronic media, he committed suicide due to caste prejudice and also because of his scholarship which has been upheld by the government. It seems that the suicide of Rohit Bemula might be one of the points burning in the mind of the novelist. The character of Satya and his suicide might be compared with the Rohit Bemula's life. Her stance is clearly visible in her affirmation in the 'Acknowledgement' of the novel when she writes in these words:

'Finally, an acknowledgement of another govt. No privileged person in terms of caste or class can, despite choices made as an adult, really, 'know' the lived experience of those who have been historically oppressed. *I Have Become the Tide* has been written with this awareness but it was also born out of the conviction that no writer can engage with life in India today without taking a stand, in some modest way, on the terrible in equalities that continue to voyage the lives of so many our fellow citizens.'" (*A Have Become the Tide*, p. 322)

Thus the stand of Githa Hariharan is quite obvious in her novels. Like Arundhati Roy, she has strong affirmation of life in her novels for different reasons altogether. Similar kind of narrative is also visible in the novels of the contemporary writers because of the same kind of stand as shown by Githa Hariharan. In *The God of Small Things*, Arundhati Roy has shown the same attitude of aggression are protest as we find the *I Have Become the Tide*. The exploitation of woman and the people belonging to lower castes has become the central issue in the thematic perceptions of literature in recent time. The outcome so-called 'dalit' literature signifies the terms and condition in better manner. The narration of these novels shows the trend of the presentation of the issues related to dalits in good manner.

The trend of dalit literature in India is nothing new. Right from the beginning, there are so many writers who are more inclined towards the presentation of the exploitation and humiliation faced by dalits in their life due to the rough behaviour of the people belonging to the so-called higher castes and classes. The emergence of new narrative in Indian writing in English seems to be limelight in the new emerging scenario.

The voice of protest in the novels of Githa Hariharan is certainly the matter of great concern for different reasons altogether. In the study of the novels of Githa Hariharan, one can notice the plea of the writer towards such problems evident in the modern society also. In the modern age, the writer does not seem to be apart from the society, and some time as an activist to share his opinion in more vibrant manner. Especially, Arundhati Roy and Githa

Hariharan are not an exception. They show their much concern towards the contemporary problems relate to the dalit communities.

The novels of Githa Hariharan are realistic in nature for different things altogether. She seems to be more sensitive writer because she boldly highlighted the inner urge of the dalits in the contemporary life. She is of the opinion that this problem an age-old problem. For her, it is the matter of great concern that such problems are still visible in so-called civilized society with some sense of transformation.

There seems to be a unique sense of reformative zeal in the works of Githa Hariharan. Her reformative zeal compels her to write such novels which are much oriented in the transformation of the society. The modern criticism which is evident in her writing is also full of consideration for different reasons altogether. The writers like Githa Hariharan does not hesitate to criticize the society which has so many shortcomings in general. People are in the modern age progressive in nature but the complications related to the modern living do not allow them to produce the desired result. The writing of protest has so many repercussions. The same was seen when *Untouchable* of Mulk Raj Anand was published. This novel was about the problem of untouchability. People might say that the problem of untouchability is not being removed by this book of Anand. But the efforts of Anand were not it vain. Certainly this book might arouse many burning questions in the minds of the people and they are forced to see the matter in the way of reformation. So, the reformative zeal of the writer cannot be denied at all.

The writings of Mulk Raj Anand might have been the source of inspiration for the writers of the new generation in terms of thematic perception related to such issues. The exploitation of the downtrodden, underdogs and underprivileged of the society is not new. It is still in continuation for different reasons altogether. The writers have become quite sensitive to look into the matter and devote much times to analyse the problem with upper hand. Their sense of documentation helps there too much to show their inclination towards the analysis of age-old problem in new way, Critics might say that the ‘old wine is being served in new bottle’. But the question is that ‘why this old wine’ is still available in the society’. This should be the matter of great concern and society should come formed to look into the matter and gives solutions to the burning problem.

Thus, the writings of Githa Hariharan are in the line of her reformative zeal. She seems to be more concerned with her active part in such matters related to the condition of the people suffered because of caste-prejudice and unsympathetic consideration. Especially her two novels— *Fugitive Histories* and *I Have Become the Tide* — are extremely important in highlighting the issues related to minorities and low caste people. She has shown an absolute kind of sympathetic and compassionate consideration towards the suffering of the people because of the hostile nature of the people belonging to opposite direction. So, the study of Githa Hariharan will certainly be fruitful in such direction for different reasons altogether.

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